

Mark 10:45: Ending the Authenticity Debate

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Abstract

Using textual criticism, this paper seeks to end the authenticity debate of Mark 10:45 by reviewing the works of Bultmann, Bousset, Loisy and Branscomb, that Mark 10:45 is an effort of the early Church tradition or a highly developed theological version of Luke's version (22:7) and influenced by Galatians. 3:13, Romans. 3:24 and 1 Corinthians 7:23. Findings have it that Mark 10:45 is authentic because it is the first written book amongst the synoptic gospels (70CE) as compared to Luke (85CE). It is therefore impossible that Mark 10:45 is a theological assertion of the latter Luke's version (22:7). While the book of Galatians (C.E 48-64), Romans (A.D 57-59) and 1 Corinthians (A.D 53-54) must have been written before Mark's gospel, it is improper to assert that the Pauline school of thought had influenced Mark 10:45, when in actual sense, Apostle Paul confessed to have been influenced in 1 Corinthians 15:3. How then will the apostle who was trained in the faith on the doctrines that were also delivered to him then turn around to influence Jesus saying in Mark 10:45?. And lastly, the current fourth edition of the Greek bible

has no textual argument or criticism of a sort concerning Mark 10:45. This is an indication that all the ancient manuscripts that led to the composition of the New Testament writings, be it the Papi, the Uncials and the Minuscules do not have any parallel variations, omissions or commission on the verse under study, thus confirming Mark 10:45 to be authentic

Key words: *authenticity, Mark 10:45, son of man, ransom, to serve, Jesus Christ.*

1.0 Introduction

Before the birth of Jesus Christ around the first century AD, there had existed a system of leadership in the Mediterranean world, known as; Boss, Autocratic or Authoritarian leadership. According to E.G, Lenski¹ and John Kautsky², this system of leadership was very beneficial to the governing class, as they exercise their absolute power on the society's resources by compelling the commoners to labour for their food supplies and pay taxes for their personal aggrandizements. While on the other hand, these commoners or subjects received nothing in return. Even in Israel, the birth place of Jesus Christ was not exempted from this pattern of leadership³. That was why Jesus could also make reference to it at the time he was addressing his disciples in Mark 10:42⁴, that;

..Οἴδατε ὅτι οἱ δοκοῦτες ἄρχειν τῶν ἐθνῶν κατακυριεύουσιν αὐτῶν καὶ οἱ μεγάλοι αὐτοῶν κατ ἐξουσιάζουσιν αὐτῶν
..You know that those who are considered rulers over the Gentiles lord it over them, and their great one's exercise authority over them (KJV).

Thus, this aforementioned system of leadership continued until there was a revolutionary form of leadership as introduced by Jesus Christ, in Mark 10:45, known as Servant Leadership. This research is therefore built around the authenticity of the phrase Mark 10:45 that the son of man came not to be served but to serve and to give his life as a ransom for many. (καὶ γὰρ ὁ μῖος τοῦ ἀνθρώπου οὐκ ἦλθεν διακονη θῆναι ἀλλὰ διακοῆσαι καὶ δοῦναι τὴν ψυχὴν αὐτοῦ λύτρον ἀντί πολλῶν,). It is a verse that came to be, following the earlier request made by the two sons of Zebedee (James and John)⁵. However, certain Bible scholars saw it as a latter addition. This

¹E.G, Lenski. *Power and Privilege*. (New York: McGraw-Hill, 1966):220

²John Kautsky. *The Politics of Aristocratic Empires*. (Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press, 1982):119

³ Watch Tower Bible and Tract Society of Pennsylvania observes that Emperor Tiberius, who governed Rome and its' colonies (including the land of Israel) was a tyrant. He formed a 10,000 Roman Praetorian guard; encamped close to Rome's walls to keep in check any uprisings against his authority among the populace. That it why it was easy for the Jews to gain advantage when they charged Jesus with treason, an offence punishable by the law of "injured majesty, which Tiberius has broadened to include virtually any insult to Caesar (See Watch Tower Bible and Tract Society of Pennsylvania. Pay Attention to Daniel's Prophecy. (Germany, Druck Und Verlag: Wachturm – Gesellschaft, Selters/Taunus, 2006) 236-238.

⁴ All scriptural citations are from the KJV of the Bible unless otherwise state.

⁵Similar passage is found in Mt. 20.28. Although here, it is the mother of James and John that is making the request on behalf of her sons; James and John. Luke does not have the saying, but in his narrative of the Last Supper, he gives a saying that has some resemblance with Mark 10:45 "For which is the greater, one who sits at table, or one

research will therefore first review various scholarship comments on the text of Mark 10:45, while suggesting vital comments that will end the debate on the authenticity of Mark 10:45. Works on the likes of Obijole, Seyoon, Kgatle, Colin, Watts, Crowther, Bultmann and Taylor would be given adequate attention in relating to the question of the authenticity of Mark 10:45.

The verse, Mark 10:45 have been hotly debated by scholars. While others argue for its authenticity, some try to discuss the various concepts imbedded in the verse. It is in light of the foregoing that this review undertakes to look again on the various strands of argument by scholars regarding the verse. The review would also uncover the gaps in their research, which gave rise to this paper.

2.0 Relevant Literature on the Authenticity of Mark 10:45

In his Ph.D thesis in 1986, titled *the death of Jesus Christ in the New Testament with particular Reference to Pauline Kerygma*. Obijole highlighted two important linguistic concepts that reflect in the scripture Mark 10:45. They include; *o uios tou anthropou* (Son of Man) and *litron* (Ransom). He took a wide consultation into the concept of *o uios tou anthropou* in the Old Testament and in the gospels. He asserts that the term Son of Man, is one of the names used by Jesus himself, about eighty times in all the gospels. While the background use of the term is in Daniel 7:13 which is written probably for the purpose of using Daniel's experience to encourage the Jews involved in the Maccabean struggles.

He concludes that Jesus knew that the son of man in Daniel was a figure of majesty; splendor and universal acclaim whose role he has come to fulfill. He also knew that the son of man in Daniel was a suffering figure- who represents the saints of the highest, who were persecuted (Daniel 7:21, 25), the whole concept to him therefore points to a suffering and exalted son of man⁶. The next concept he discusses is *litpron* ransom saying in Mark 10:45. He affirms that the ransom saying occurs in Mathew 20:28 and Mark 10:45. Thereafter, he took a swipe at

who serves? Is it not the one who sits at table? But I am among you as one who serves 'ἐγὼ δὲ ἐν μέσῳ ὑμῶν εἰμι ὁ διακονῶν' (Lk. 22:27) (See B, Colin. *Dictionary of New Testament Theology*. Vol 3,(Grand Rapids: The Zondervan Corporation, 1978:)192.

⁶ Obijole, O.O. *The death of Jesus Christ in the New Testament with particular Reference to Pauline Kerygma*, 12

Bultmann⁷, Titus, Todt⁸ who regards the Lucan version as more original (for which is greater, one who sits at table? But I am among you as one who serves) and that Mark and Mathew formed their conception of Jesus from the redemption theories, of Hellenistic Christianity.

He thus agrees with Moulder that the Markan and Mathean version are genuine words of Jesus. Luke instead appears to have made a deliberate alteration of the original saying. In the process of doing so, Luke has more or less watered down the deep meaning of the original saying. It is more reasonable suppose that the saying in Mark 10:45 (Mathew 20:28) is more original because of its depth of meaning than to imagine that it is secondary to Luke 22:27. On the theological meaning of Mark 10:45, Obijole suggests that the verse outlines the theological role that Christ has come to fulfill. Jesus double role as the Son of Man and servant is outlined. The verse summarizes the evangelists Christology of the crucifixion. The son of Man has come to live on earth as servant⁹.

On the issue of the argument of Mark 10:45 allusion to Daniel 12:3, 11:33-34 and Isaiah 53:6-15, he opposes Todt and Barrett's proposition that the phrase *anti pollon* (for many) is far from proving with certainty that there is a reference to Isa. 53. He however agrees with McKenzie that the phrase *anti pollon* (for many) seems reminiscent of the servant of Yahweh mission in Isaiah 53:6 & 15. That the concept in the aforementioned verse is that of one man who will justify many; in the same manner that Jesus saw his mission as that of one who has come to serve and give his life as ransom to redeem many (Mark 10:45b + c)¹⁰.

Finally, the author moves on to draw out the conceptual meaning of λυτρον in biblical usage as having three principal meanings. It could mean payment as equivalent for a life destroyed, (Exodus. 21:30) or price for redemption of a slave (Leviticus. 25:51) or propiation for the sins of others (Proverbs. 13:8 cf 1 Tim. 2:6). Whichever way ransom is viewed, he concludes that *lutron anti pollon* (ransom for many) is a plain declaration of the sacrificial and vicarious nature of the death of our Lord. It also implies the voluntary offering of self by Jesus. To him, Mark 10:45 is one of the few theological statements in the gospels that summarizes the evangelists Christology and understanding of the crucifixion¹¹. Obijole's work on Mark 10:45 is a pointer towards the

⁷ Bultmann, *Theology of the New Testament*. 152

⁸ Todt, *Son of Man in Synoptic Tradition*. 44.

⁹ Obijole. *Death of Jesus Christ*, 17.

¹⁰ *Ibid*, 17

¹¹ Obijole, *Death of Jesus Christ in New Testament*, (1986): 18-19.

evangelists' Christology of the crucifixion in reference to the death of Jesus Christ in the New Testament. Although he discusses the concept of *ho uios tou anthropou* and *litron* in Mark 10:45 and also recognizes the fact that the son of man has come to live on earth as servant, he has not satisfactorily given solution to the authenticity of Mark 10:45, a gap that this research intends to fill.

In his 117-page book on *The Son of Man as the Son of God*, Kim deals explicitly with the concept of *ὁ τῶν ἀνθρώπων* in the gospels, the son of man as Jesus self-designation, its background and terminology, the authenticity of Mk. 10:45, the logion in Mark 10:45, spoken at the last supper, the Old Testament background of Mk. 10:45, and the interpretation of Mk 10:45 among others. On the authenticity of Mark 10:45, he recognizes the argument by P. Stuhlmacher who demonstrates the authenticity of the verse in fourfold; first he links Mk 10:45 with 2 Tim. 2:5 as having similar semitizing wordings. Second is Mk 10:45 and Isa. 53, noting that only the following concepts are common; *(παρα)-διδόναι, ψυχη, αὐτοῦ, πολλοί*. And that, these are sufficient to confirm the dependency of Mark 10:45 on Isa 53, but not its origin from the Church's interpretation of Isa 53¹².

Third and fourth is the verb *διακονεῖν* in Mark 10:45 with the Aramaic root. This root appears in the Old Testament only once, namely in Daniel 7:10 where the service of thousands of angels before God is spoken of. In Daniel 7:13, the Son of Man receives kinship all over the nations and in 1 En 45:3; 61:8, 62:2, he appears on God's throne of judgment and the nations fall before him and the angels serve him. Thus, the tradition-historical context of *διακονεῖν* of Mk. 10:45 is the glorious "Son of Man" tradition of Dn 7 and the Similitude of Enoch¹³. Against those that sees Mk. 10:45 as a secondary verse, Kim argues that if with the Son of Man- *ἦλθεν* sayings, early Christians and the evangelists had wanted to convey the sense of the retrospective perspective on Jesus historical appearance as a whole, they would not have placed them in the mouth of the Son of Man Jesus, but in their own mouths as narrators.¹⁴ Seyoon's argument for the authenticity of Mark 10:45 could not sufficiently address or end the debate, a gap that this research intends to fill.

¹² Seyoon, *Son of Man*, 37-38

¹³ Ibid, 39.

¹⁴ Kgatle, *Servant Leadership in Mark 10:35-45*, (2015): 42

In his focus on his Ph.D thesis in 2015 on servant leadership in Mark 10:35-45 applied to African Pentecostal Christianity. He used a synchronic approach to interpret the verse in question. To him, Mark 10:35-45 is divided into two aspects: first is the request made by the two sons of Zebedee in Mk 10:35-40 and second, Jesus' response in Mark 10:41-45. For this is aimed at understanding leadership misconceptions of the two sons of Zebedee in Mark 10:35-40 and servant leadership principles by Jesus in Mk 10:41-45.

Under leadership misconception, Kgatle identifies five types of leadership misconception as embedded in Mk 10:35-45. First is kinship misconception; this is where the author traces the family ties of Zebedee (James and John), as close relatives of Jesus Christ. Therefore, they took advantage of this kind of relationship by making the request as benefactors of family relationship. Secondly, is self-interest and ambition misconception: it is found in verse 35 of Mark, where James and John came to Jesus saying; we desire that you do for us whatever we shall ask, that; while it is not wrong to be ambitious, it is also not right to appeal for favors that benefit only the individual asking for it. No wonder, their request (James and John) made other disciples indignant against them¹⁵. Thirdly, is position and community misconception; a place where James and John asked for places of honour in the kingdom. They believed that Jesus would not only die on the cross, but resurrect as king and also restore the kingdom of God. This after all was Jesus' statement about his death that made James and John to request for places of honour in his kingdom. Given their fore knowledge about this, they certainly did not want to miss out on that opportunity to sit next to the king. That this is nothing but selfish hunger for positions of authority¹⁶. Fourth, is competition misconception; Kgatle identifies this in verse 41 of Mark 10, where the other ten disciples became indignant on hearing the request made by James and John. The author identifies Thurston's position on the matter. He believes that the other ten disciples could have become angry based on two reasons: first is either they were trying to defend Jesus' teachings on discipleship and greatness in the kingdom (Mk 9:30-50) or they were equally interested in contesting with James and John for positions of authority in the kingdom¹⁷.

¹⁵ Idid, 81.

¹⁶ Ibid, 86.

¹⁷ Ibid, 92

The latter view is more enforced, especially with the likes of Earle, Blarney and Harson. That the other ten were angry at this request of James and John, probably because they too were harbouring the same vision for power. They possibly wanted the only two limited seats in the kingdom, but were angry that they have been occupied. Lastly, is Lordship and authority misconception; that in verse 42 of Mark 10, James and John wanted the same kind of leadership as practiced by the Gentiles. For they take advantage of power, abuse it and compel others to obey them. However, in Jesus' kingdom, a leader has to become a servant (Mk 10:45)¹⁸. Secondly, are servant leadership principles by Jesus in Mk 10:41-45. Kgatle identifies this in Mark 10:38-39, where Jesus asked his disciples, are you able to drink of the cup that I drink and be baptized with the baptism that I shall be baptized with? And the disciples replied, yes, we can. That this demonstrates that servant leadership is all about suffering and sacrifice. In Mk. 10:40, Jesus says, ...to sit on my right hand and my left hand is not mine to give but for those to whom it is prepared, this demonstrates that servant leadership is from God, the father. The last response in Mk. 10:43-44 that whoever must be great among you shall first be your servant and whosoever of you shall be chief must be servant of all, demonstrates that leadership is all about servant hood¹⁹.

Kgatle also traces the historical background of African Pentecostal Church, described to apply servant leadership in a relevant manner. The author also investigates the origins of worldwide Pentecostal movement in order to understand the historical origins of African Pentecostal Christianity. Identified leadership misconceptions in Mark are applied to leadership misconceptions in African Pentecostal Christianity. Apostolic Faith Church of South Africa is singled out as an African Pentecostal Christian Church. The author concludes with the use of reader response criticism in comparing leadership misconception in Mark and African Pentecostal Church, but fails to address the question of the authenticity of Mark 10:45. This is the gap that this research intends to fill.

In his introduction to New Testament book, Volume 3 in 1932, the author takes a swipe at the linguistic aspect of Mark 10:45 especially on the word “*λιτρον*” before he arrived at the phrase in Mark 10:45, he first traces the word in light of ancient Greek background using D.Hill's Greek

¹⁸Kgatle, *Servant Leadership in Mark 10:35-45*, (2015): 96.

¹⁹Ibid, 103.

words and their Hebrew meanings²⁰ that *lytron* (from 5th Cent. B.C, on) and *antilytron* (only Post Biblical in secular Greek) denotes the means or money for a ransom. The suffix *-tron* denote the instrument or means by which the action of the verb is accomplished, i.e means of releasing or the payment, i.e price of releasing²¹.

He continues that among the Greeks, a ransom was often paid to free slaves but the word is seldom found in cultic contexts. *Lytroo* (from Plato on) means to free by a ransom, redeem. It is used only in act. in secular Greek, but is always middle or passive. In biblical Greek, *Lytrōsis* and *apolytrōsis* synonyms, meaning freeing, redeeming, are rare and found first in 1st. Cent. B.C. *lytrotes*, redeemer, is found only in biblical Gk. In the LXX, the singular *Lytronis* found only in Lev. 27:31; Prov. 6:35; 13:8; otherwise, it's always in plural²². Colin also made a spectacular discovery about the Jewish beliefs of the atoning value of suffering and martyrdom in the immediate pre-Christian era. Traditionally, atonement was achieved through the sacrifices of the cult and the Day of Atonement, but after the destruction of the temple and the cessation of sacrifice, it came to be thought of in terms of obedience and suffering, especially death. That the idea of man's death atoning for his own sins is not traceable in pre-Christian Judaism, but the idea of representative atonement is pre-Christian²³.

In the New Testament, Brown Colin identifies the concept *λυτρον* to be found only in the sayings of Jesus, which apart from introductory conjunctions is found with identical wording in Matt. 20:28 and Mark 10:45. He also recognizes the arguments put forward for and against the authenticity of Mark 10:45 especially the one by Rudolf Bultmann that Mark 10:45 is a later theological addition by the Church. However, he disputes the claim as indemonstrable. The author also traces the background of Mk. 10:45 in light of the Palestinian background, and in allusion to the suffering servant of Isaiah 53, especially verse 10-12, noting the works of reputable scholars whom have also drawn their support in light of the aforementioned backgrounds. One of them is William Lane who throws in support for Mark 10:45 affiliations

²⁰ Hill, *Greek Words and Hebrew Meanings* 5, 49.

²¹ Colin, *λύτρον*' Dictionary of New Testament, Grand Rapids: (The Zondervan Corporation, 1932):189

²²Ibid, 193.

²³Ibid, 194.

with Isaiah 53²⁴. But his argument has not sufficiently ended the debate of the authenticity of Mark 10:45. This is the gap that this paper intends to fill.

In his book in *Isaiah's New Exodus in Mark* in 1997, Watts²⁵ discusses deeply on the passion predictions and Mark 10:45, Three (3) aspect of Mark 10:45 dominates his review; they include; the various backgrounds, particularly Isaiah's influence and the LXX allusion to the verse in question, then the concept of service and ransom. In carrying out his task, he first reviews some of the arguments for and against Isaiah's influence on the text to which they lead. First, he finds the purpose of the coming son of man in Mark 10:45b; adding that the verse (10:45b) ought not to be segregated from the prediction of Mark 10:32-34. For this is indicated by a consistent repatriate structure of A) prediction (8:31; 9:31; 10:32) B) failure to understand (8:32-33; 9:32; 10:35-41) and C) subsequent teaching (8:34-38; 9:35-37; 10:42-45)²⁶

Mark 10:45 according to Watts review on the various arguments have been broken down into two: namely Mark 10:45a (οὐκ ἦλθεν διακονη θῆναι ἀλλὰ διακοῆσαι) and Mark 10:45b. (δοῦναι τὴν ψυχὴν αὐτοῦ λύτρον ἀντὶ πολλῶν). With regard to the former, it was held that the service envisaged alluded to that of a "servant" although Hooker argues that the root διακονεω appears in different Greek words in the LXX, particularly δουλους and δουλευω appears in Isaiah 40-45, while παις is preferred of a 'servant' διακονεω is not among them. For him the 'servant' concept in Isaiah is directed towards God but in the Mark 10:45, it is towards others²⁷. Watts however fails to talk about the authenticity of Mark 10:45, as if it is not a serious issue. This is the gap created that gave rise to this paper.

In his book on the *Gospel according to Mark*, in 1966, Vincent Taylor writes on the authenticity of Mark 10:45. He questions the genuineness of the saying and traces its form to Pauline influence. He mentions Wellhausen, who feels the verse is out of harmony with its context. The change from the idea of service to that of the giving of life as a ransom, he argues, is a μετ βασις εἰς αλλογενος, a transition from one class (of ideas) to another, and is derived from the tradition of the Last Supper where Jesus, with bread and wine, dispenses His flesh and blood. In the same vein, Branscomb, also thinks that Mark 10:45 is a highly developed theological version of Lk.

²⁴Colin, 'λύτρον' Dictionary of New Testament, Grand Rapids: (The Zondervan Corporation, 1932): 195.

²⁵ Watts, *Isaiah's New Exodus in Mark*. (Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 1997).

²⁶ Ibid, 271

²⁷ Ibid, 271

22:27, influenced by Gal. 3:13, Rom. 3:24, and 1 Cor 7:23. He agrees that such explanations have been overstated, and that many of Paul's most characteristic ideas are wanting in Mk, but holds that 'the Gospel belongs undoubtedly to the Pauline school-that is, one which viewed Christianity essentially as a religion of redemption through the death of the Messiah'²⁸

This position commensurate with Seyoon's position of Mark 10:45 alluded to the event of the last supper. J. Weiss, also suggests that in the saying, the whole life and work of Jesus are seen in retrospect (ἠλθεν). Ἀύθρον and the ideas suggested by it appear nowhere else in the preaching of Jesus and the original form of the saying is to be seen in Lk. xxii. 27, which says nothing of a redemptive death²⁹. While Jesus may have included His death in His work of service and of love for men, it is doubtful if He thought of it as sacrificial or as involving penal suffering, as, according to later interpretation. The author also quotes both Bousset, and Bultmann, who agrees that the saying is a dogmatic recast of Lk. 22:27³⁰.

Similarly, Loisy, also thinks that Mark has borrowed the theory of redemption, from Paul. Rashdall's treatment of the saying in *The Idea of the Atonement* is well known. The only doctrine of the Atonement, he holds, which can be traced to Jesus Himself is ' the simple doctrine that his death, like His life, was a piece of service or self-sacrifice for His followers, such as they themselves might very well make for one another', On the other side the author cites Rawlinson, who thinks that the saying, despite its omission by Luke, is in all probability genuine and that the reference to ' the many ' is an echo of Isa.53:11 ff. that the ' ransom' metaphor sums up the general thought of Isa. 53, and expresses the idea of a vicarious and voluntary giving up of life, with the thought also implied that the sacrifice was in some way mysteriously necessitated by sin³¹.

In reply to Loisy, Lagrange, points out that not only the redemptive death is known to Paul, but also the thought of service unto death (Phil. 2:7 ff.), and asks the pertinent question whether Jesus has furnished the theme for the Pauline developments or Mark has summarized in a word

²⁸ Taylor, Gospel according to Mark, London: The Macmillan Press, (1966):445

²⁹ Ibid, 445.

³⁰ Ibid, 445-6

³¹ Taylor, Gospel according to Mark, London: The Macmillan Press, (1966): 445-6

the theology of Paul in order to attribute it to Jesus. The former hypothesis, he holds, is the only one that is probable. Howard, *ET*, finds the key to the saying in Isa. 53. The significant word, he observes, is not Pauline. In Pauline circles the form of the logion is most characteristically seen in 1 Tim. 2: 6 ('a ransom *for all*') and Tit. 2:14 ('*forus*'). The answers given in the Early Church to the questions provoked by the Cross are interpretations of the luminous hint which Jesus gave to His perplexed disciples in such sayings as Mk. 10:45 and 14:24³².

The strength of the argument, Taylor concludes is on the affirmative side. Those who deny the genuineness of the saying too easily assume that its ideas are exclusively Pauline and do not sufficiently recognize that Paulinism is rooted in primitive Christianity. Adequate consideration is not given to the possibility that Lk. 22:27 is an independent saying. Again, notably in the case of Weiss, the rejection of Mk. 10:45 is influenced by the desire to avoid older doctrines of the Atonement which have found shelter under the saying and to obtain a purely general interpretation of its meaning. It is wise never to forget that *λύτρον* is used metaphorically, but it is equally wise to remember that a metaphor is used to convey an arresting thought. Jesus died to fulfill the Servant's destiny and His service is that of vicarious and representative suffering. We are ill-advised if we seek to erect a theory upon 10:45 alone, but equally so if we dismiss it as a product of later theological construction. Taylor Vincent's focus on trying to verify the authenticity of Mark 10:45 is well appreciated, although it does not sufficiently end the debate of the authenticity of Mark 10:45. This is the gap we are trying to fill here.

Crowder Steven in his article on *Re-examining Servant Leadership in the Gospel of Mark* in 2018 focuses on the distinction between the two types of leadership in Mark 10:40-45, along with a comparison of contemporary servant leadership. First, he identifies verse 42 of Mark 10, where the great leaders of the Gentiles exercise authority over others. That whereas, when Jesus turns to kingdom leadership, he says that the great leaders become servants, when on the other hand, the world's leadership is rooted in exercising something-an activity. That this is then a key

³² Ibid, 445-6.

verse in this periscope where Jesus is explaining to his disciples the ingredients to great leadership. The key ingredient is to be a servant like the Son of Man³³.

He states that there are two important pieces to understanding this comparison. First, it was in response to the two disciples clamoring for greatness. Jesus then declared greatness to be through becoming a servant. That Jesus does not resist their desires to be great, but he changes the path to greatness. Secondly is the implication that Jesus set the example in becoming a servant. He served them in such a way that their lives changed by his encounter with them. During the last supper, Jesus consolidated many of the concepts of servant hood, leadership and greatness in the kingdom of God, and by washing the disciples' feet, he set the example and called them to follow it. While he did not dissuade his disciples from greatness, he showed them the way to greatness by becoming a servant and by living life in connection with God³⁴. The author supports Mark 10:45 allusion to Isaiah 53:11. He went further to identify other Old Testament passages in Isaiah, that are echoed in Mark 10:45, particularly those about sacrifice and offerings for sin and Yahweh's redemptive work for Israel (Isaiah 35:9, 41:14, 43:1, 44:22-24, 52:3, 62:12, 63:9). Crowther however does not discuss on the authenticity of the verse. This is the gap created that this research intends to fill.

In his works on *Theology of the New Testament and History of the Synoptic Tradition*³⁵ in 1976-77, Bultmann talks about "The Question of the Messianic Consciousness of Jesus, leading to the synoptic Son of Man title, found also in Mark 10:45 and the authenticity of the verse. On the question of the Messianic Consciousness of Jesus, he posits that:

...the church of Jesus disciples understood his claim that men's destiny is determined by their attitude to him in such a way that they regarded Jesus himself as the Messiah they had been expecting, or else still awaited Jesus himself as the coming son of man. The common opinion is that this belief of the earliest church rests upon the self-consciousness of Jesus, i.e that he

³³Crowther. "The Spirit of Service," Retrieved from https://www.regent.edu/acad/global/publications/innerresources/vol1iss3/crowther_spirituality.pdf 1

³⁴ Ibid, 2

³⁵ Bultmann, *Theology of New Testament*. Vol. 8, New York: Charles Scribner & Sons, (1980). 412.

actually did consider himself to be the Messiah, or the son of man...It does agree with the evangelist's point of view, but the question is whether they themselves have not superimposed upon the traditional material their own belief in the messiahship of Jesus³⁶.

What Rudolf Bultmann (1976-77) is trying to bring out here is if Jesus was actually the one who considered himself as the Messiah or it was just a belief of the early church imposed upon him. The reply Bultmann gave is that it is a later early church belief about Jesus. It is simply a pure act of faith. He goes further to categorize the synoptic son of man sayings into three groups. As one which speak of the Son of Man (i) as coming (ii) as suffering, death and rising again, and (iii) as now at work. He regards the third group as found in Mark 2:10, 28; Mathew. 8:20 par, 11:19 par 12:32 par, and owes its origin to a mere misunderstanding of the translation into Greek. That in Aramaic, the son of man in these sayings was not a messianic title at all but meant "man, or "I,"³⁷

For the second group, he says it contains the vaticinia ex eventu which are not yet present in Q, while the first group alone contains very old tradition. The sayings belonging to it speak of the son of man belonging to the third person, thereby concluding that the term "son of man, is simply the designation of the early church concerning Jesus. See how he puts it;

...now it is true that in the predictions of the passion the Jewish concept Messiah-Son-of-Man is re-interpreted-or better, singularly enriched-insofar as the idea of a suffering, dying, rising Messiah or Son of Man was unknown to Judaism. But this re-interpretation of the concept was done not by Jesus himself but by the church ex eventu... the attempt is made to carry the idea of the suffering Son of Man back into Jesus own outlook by assuming that Jesus regarded himself as Deutro-Isaiah's servant of God who suffers and dies for the sinner, and fuse together the two ideas Son of Man and Servant of God into the single figure of the suffering, dying, and rising Son of Man.³⁸

³⁶ Bultmann. *Theology of New Testament*, New York: Charles Scribner & Sons, (1980). 26.

³⁷Ibid, 30.

³⁸ Bultmann. *Theology of New Testament*, New York: Charles Scribner & Sons, (1980).

In other words, Bultmann posits that the tradition of Jesus sayings reveals no trace of a consciousness on his part of being the servant of God of Isaiah 53. To him, the messianic interpretation of Is. 53 was discovered in the Christian Church and even in it evidently not immediately. That the synoptic predictions of the passion obviously do not have Isa. 53 in mind, otherwise, why is it nowhere referred to? Only later do such specific references as 1 Clem. 16:3-14 and Barn. 5:2 come along³⁹. On the issue of the authenticity of Mark 10:45, the author concludes that the Lucan saying is more original than the Marcan. He sees the Marcan version as a product of the early church in the form of an utterance attributed to the exalted Christ⁴⁰. Since Bultmann does not believe in the authenticity of Mark 10:45, a vacuum created, which calls for this research.

2.1 Scriptural Review

Mark 10:45 stands authenticated by textual and doctrinal harmony as this section reveals. The debate over the authenticity of Mark 10:45 where Jesus declares, for even the Son of Man did not come to be served, but to serve, and to give His life as a ransom for many, centers on whether this verse is an original saying of Jesus or a later theological insertion influenced by early Christian tradition⁴¹. This paper defends its authenticity by examining historical, textual-critical evidence, and doctrinal coherence. Beyond that, it is, however, believed, that *Scriptura sui ipsius interpres*⁴² (Scripture is its own interpreter). Hence, the need for a Scriptural cross-validation to test the consistency of this passage with divine truth that Jesus is the original author of this statement. This is done through scriptural review framework.

Starting from the immediate contextual discourse in Mark 10: 35-45, Jesus told the three sons of Zebedee, James and John, that the greatness in the Kingdom of God is through servanthood. The climactic theological grounding is found in verse 45: “For even the son of man came not to be

30

³⁹ Ibid, 31

⁴⁰ Ibid, 149

⁴¹ Bultmann. *Theology of New Testament*, New York: Charles Scribner & Sons, (1980).

²⁶ Kim, S. *The Son of Man as the Son of God*. Mohr, (1983).

⁴² This is a Latin phrase, which translates to “Scripture is its own interpreter”. This concept is rooted in biblical hermeneutics, meaning that the Bible is its own interpreter. And that the Bible should be understood through internal consistency and cross-referencing within the text itself.

ministered unto, but to minister, and to give his life a ransom for many, (KJV). Matthew 20:28 parallels Mark 10:45, which demonstrates independent attestation in Synoptic tradition. Philippians 2: 5-8 echoes the same theme – servanthood in leadership. The prophecy in Isaiah 53:10-12: “...for he shall bear their iniquities... and he bare the sin of many,..., aligns perfectly with Mark’s “his life a ransom for many., Paul, the Apostle, reaffirms the same concept in 1Timothy 2:5-6, “...the man Christ Jesus; Who gave himself a ransom for all,..., This scriptural consistency affirms ransom-servant motif and a testimony to the statement made by Jesus in Mark 10:45.

Theologically, Mark 10:45 captures two theological pillars: Christology and Soteriology. Indeed, theology must be biblical and “Any Christian theology that does not take its root in God’s Word is *atheology*,(Dele Ilesanmi, 2025).⁴³ Thus, the Bible is integral to our theology. Christologically, the Messianic title, “the Son of Man, in the book of Daniel 7:13-14, shows Jesus’ divine authority but embraces servanthood. Soteriologically, Jesus’ death is vicarious and redemptive – “a ransom for many., Indeed, this shows substitutionary atonement. These two theological themes are well rooted in both Old and New Testament theology, which further strengthening the authenticity of Mark 10:45.

In summary, no doctrine derived from Mark 10: 45 contradicts the rest of Scripture. Instead, it reinforces: (1) Servanthood as Kingdom greatness (John 13:14-15); (2) Substitutionary atonement (2Cor 5:21); and (3) Christ’s mission of redemption (Luke 19:10). Therefore, Jesus’ statement in Mark 10:45 is doctrinally sound and not an interpolation as many scholars perceived. It is a core revelation of Jesus’ mission; it is contextually consistent and scripturally corroborated across the Bible, theologically profound, doctrinally aligned, and faith-affirming. It is believed that this scriptural cross-validation will end the authenticity debate.

⁴³ For a comprehensive understanding, see Ilesanmi, Dele A. “The Imperative of Scriptural Review in Biblical Research Studies: A Proposal for Paradigm Shift from Literature Review” in *Mature Journal of International Institute of Christian Theologians, Scholars, and Professionals*, 2025.

3.0 Authenticity of Mark 10:45: Ending the Debate

Having reviewed the various authors that directly or indirectly discussed the verse of Mark 10:45, many argue for its authenticity and others disagree with it as a latter deliberate imposition from the ancient Christian tradition. Scholars such as Bultmann argues against the authenticity of Mark 10:45; posing it as a later theological addition by the Church. He agrees with scholars as indicated above that the Lucan saying is more original than the Marcan. He sees the Marcan version as a product of the early church in the form of an utterance attributed to the exalted Christ⁴⁴. However, Colin Brown disputes the claim as indemonstrable. V. Taylor⁴⁵ traces Mark 10:45 to Pauline influence. He feels the verse is out of harmony with its context. The change from the idea of service to that of the giving of life as a ransom, he argues, is a μετασῆσις εἰς ἄλλο γένος, a transition from one class (of ideas) to another, and is derived from the tradition of the Last Supper where Jesus, with bread and wine, dispenses His flesh and blood.

Just like Bultmann, Bousset⁴⁶, also agrees that the saying is a dogmatic recast of Luke 22: 27. Similarly, Loisy thinks that the idea of ransom, was alien to Jesus. For Mark could have borrowed it from the theory of redemption, from Rashdall's treatment of the saying in *The Idea of the Atonement*, 49-56; is well known. The only doctrine of the Atonement, he holds, which can be traced to Jesus Himself is ' the simple doctrine that His death, like His life, was a piece of service or self-sacrifice for His followers, such as they themselves might very well make for one another.⁴⁷ Branscomb, also thinks that Mark 10:45 is a highly developed theological version of Luke 22:27, influenced by Galatians. 3:13, Romans. 3:24, and 1 Corinthians 7:23. He agrees that the Gospel belongs undoubtedly to the Pauline school-that is, one which viewed Christianity essentially as a religion of redemption through the death of the Messiah⁴⁸ In my assertion therefore, Mark 10:45 can be said to be authentic, owing to the fact that a common ground has been reached amongst scholars of contemporary times⁴⁹ that the book of Mark is the first written book amongst the synoptic gospels (70CE) as compared to Luke (85CE). It is therefore

⁴⁴ Op.cit, 149

⁴⁵ Taylor, *Gospel according to Mark*, London: The Macmillan Press, (1966): 445

⁴⁶ Bousset, *Kyrios Christos*,

⁴⁷ Qtd in V. Taylor, *Gospel according to Mark*, London: The Macmillan Press, (1966): 445.

⁴⁸ Ibid 445

⁴⁹ See A.Y, Collins. *Mark*. (Minneapolis: Fortress, 2007)

impossible that Mark 10:45 is a theological assertion of the latter Luke's version (22:7). Secondly, while the book of Galatians (C.E 48-64), Romans (A.D 57-59) and 1Corinthians (A.D 53-54) must have been written before Mark's gospel, it is improper to assert that the Pauline school of thought must have influenced Mark 10:45, when in actual sense, Apostle Paul confessed to have been influenced in 1Corinthians 15:3 that "...I delivered to you first of all that which I also received...., This implies that he was also taught what he now knows. How then will the apostle or those he trained in the faith on the doctrines that was also delivered to him then turn around to influence Jesus' saying in Mark 10:45?

On the contrary, L. Marie Joseph has argued that the idea of an expiatory death is not dependent on Hellenistic Christianity since this concept was well known in contemporary Judaism. Isaiah 53.10 witnesses the possibility of giving one's life as 'guilt offering'. 4 Maccabees 17.22-23 speaks of the devout Jews executed by the tyrant Antiochus as giving their lives as *ἱλαστήριον* (a means of expiation). In 2 Macc. 17.23, it is said that the deaths of Jewish martyrs are able 'to stop the wrath of the Almighty'. These texts show the familiarity of first-century Palestinian Jews. So, Jesus Christ being among them, with the idea of sacrificial death; is perfectly plausible. Therefore, the allusion that Jesus could have applied it to himself is absolutely possible than to reject that he had no knowledge of such an idea,⁵⁰

Next to L. Marie – Joseph, V. Taylor, who has also argued that there is no reason to consider v. 45b a creation of Pauline theology operating in Mark. The idea of redemptive death is present both in Mark and Paul because of a common tradition and not because Mark borrowed it from Paul. According to V. Taylor, this tradition can be traced back to Jesus⁵¹. Another argument, favouring the authenticity of Mark 10:45 is Gundry's projection of Semitism in Mark 10.45. He says that this semitic is the paratactic (*καί*) used exegetically to mean (*by*). Gundry argues that 'these Semitisms demand a pre-Markan origin. According to R.H, Gundry, 10.45b could not have existed in the tradition by itself, but were connected already to 10.45a. This is what he says; "It seems unlikely that a saying dealing simply with service and set in a periscope dealing only with service should have been given a soteriological twist without dominical support, especially since indisputably Christian formulations concerning Jesus' death do not use the vocabulary of service.

⁵⁰ Marie-Joseph, *Evangile selon saint Marc*, (Marc Paris: J. Gabalda, 1966):283.

⁵¹ Taylor, *Gospel according to Mark*, London: The Macmillan Press, (1966): 445-46.

He concludes that “We should not disallow out of hand the possibility of Jesus' coming to believe and teach that his death will carry salvific value,⁵². In my submission therefore, even though the proponents of Mark 10:45 have tried to make the verse authentic, nothing can be more authentic when the text of Mark 10:45 has been cleared through the current fourth edition of the Greek bible. There is no textual argument or criticism of a sort concerning Mark 10:45. This is an indication that all the ancient manuscripts that led to the composition of the New Testament writings, be it the Papi, the Uncials and the Minuscules do not have any parallel variations, omissions or commission on the verse under study, thus confirming Mark 10:45 to be authentic⁵³.

4.0 Conclusion

This article has reviewed the works of renowned scholars on the authenticity of Mark 10:45 that say ‘the son of man came not to be served but to serve and to give His life as a ransom for many’. Those who feel Mark 10:45 was a latter addition includes Bultmann, Bousset, Loisy and Branscomb. They argue that Mark 10:45 is an effort of the early Church tradition or a highly developed theological version of Luke’s version (22:7) and influenced by Galatians. 3:13, Romans. 3:24 and 1 Corinthians 7:23. That, the Gospel belongs undoubtedly to the Pauline school-that is, one which viewed Christianity essentially as a religion of redemption through the death of the Messiah, thereby implying that Mark 10:45 must have been added or crafted by this Pauline school of thought. On the other hand, scholars like Marie – Joseph, V. Taylor, O. Obijole, Seyoon Kim and Brown Colin argue that Mark 10:45 is authentic but failed to give convincing reasons for its’ authenticity. But Mark 10:45 can be said to be authentic reason being that a common ground has been reached amongst scholars of contemporary times⁵⁴ that the book of Mark is the first written book amongst the synoptic gospels (70CE) as compared to Luke (85CE). It is therefore impossible that Mark 10:45 is a theological assertion of the latter Luke’s version (22:7). Secondly, while the book of Galatians (C.E 48-64), Romans (A.D 57-59) and 1Corinthians (A.D 53-54) must have been written before Mark’s gospel, it is improper to assert that the Pauline school of thought must have influenced Mark 10:45, when in actual sense,

⁵² Gundry, *Mark: A Commentary*, 588-89.

⁵³ Aland, et al, eds, *Greek New Testament*, 164.

⁵⁴ See A.Y, Collins. *Mark*. (Minneapolis: Fortress, 2007)

Apostle Paul confessed to have been influenced in 1Corinthians 15:3 that “ ...I delivered to you first of all that which I also received..., This implies that he was also taught what he now knows. How then will the apostle or those he trained in the faith on the doctrines that was also delivered to him then turn around to influence Jesus’ saying in Mark 10:45? And lastly, the current fourth edition of the Greek bible has no textual argument or criticism of a sort concerning Mark 10:45. This is an indication that all the ancient manuscripts that led to the composition of the New Testament writings, be it the Papi, the Uncials and the Minuscules do not have any parallel variations, omissions or commission on the verse under study, thus confirming Mark 10:45 to be authentic

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